

Conceptual Perimeter Model for Estimating Building Envelope Quantities

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Abstract—Building girth is important in building economics and mostly used in quantities take-off of various cost items. Literature suggests that the use of conceptual quantities can improve the accuracy of cost models. Girth or perimeter of a building can be used to estimate conceptual quantities. Hence, the current paper aims to model the perimeter-area function of buildings shapes for use at the conceptual design stage. A detailed literature review on existing building shape indexes was carried out. An empirical approach was used to study the relationship between area and the shortest length of a four-sided orthogonal polygon. Finally, a mathematical approach was used to establish the observed relationships. The empirical results obtained were in agreement with the mathematical model developed. A new equation termed “conceptual perimeter equation” is proposed. The equation can be used to estimate building envelope quantities such as external wall area, external finishing area and scaffolding area before sketch or detailed drawings are prepared.

Keywords—Building envelope, building shape index, conceptual quantities, cost modelling, girth.

I. INTRODUCTION

PROJECT cost control is an important process used to improve the cost performance of construction projects, and also a key performance index of construction projects [1]. Cost control is an iterative process of measuring, evaluating and adjusting progress, plans and finance [2]. One of the purposes of cost control is to achieve a balanced expenditure on various building elements within agreed amounts. Thus, ensuring that final accounts approximately equals the budget estimate [3], [4]. The need to address the stated purpose of controlling cost has led to several academic research studies in the field of construction economics. Cost modelling is one of the research areas that have been documented since 1951 [5]. Cost models have provided critical insights into variables or factors that affect the cost of construction at an early pre-design or conceptual stage of building projects [6]-[9].

Conceptual estimates are critical for resource planning at the early stages of a project [10], [11]. Until recently, research on conceptual cost of construction overlooks conceptual quantities in detail during model development. Reference [12], [13], with a view to reducing the prediction error in conceptual cost estimates, advocates for the use of building element quantities and construction material quantities in prediction models. Reference [14] had posited that accurate estimation of material quantities for a project has a significant effect on the overall accuracy of the final cost. The perimeter-area function

of buildings is a physical attribute that can be observed in cost modelling variables such as gross floor area, and building footprint. The growth of buildings (building allometry) can also be studied using the perimeter-area function and integrated into conceptual cost models. Hence, exploring the perimeter-area function of buildings and corresponding conceptual quantities can lead to improvements in the accuracy of cost models.

The aim of the current research is not to measure cost effectiveness of building shapes. Rather, the need to estimate the girth of a building for any given floor area at the conceptual or pre-design stage is a key purpose of the research. The building girth can be used in conjunction with cost model variables like number of floors and height of building to model building element and material quantities. In order to achieve the stated purpose, empirical and mathematical approaches were adopted to study the relationship between the area and perimeter of a four-sided orthogonal shape. The major contribution of the current work is the development of a mathematical model for conceptual perimeter of buildings envelopes. Using the developed model in estimating the quantities of building envelope items, the certainty and accuracy of conceptual cost models could be increased.

II. BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

A. Theoretical Framework of Building Shape Indexes

Index numbers are measures of changes in observable phenomena [15], [16]. Although the most notable uses of index numbers are with cost, price, population, production, and employment, which are all time related phenomena [17], [18]. Index numbers can be applied to any observable physical process to describe any measure of change within or during the process. Building shape index can thus be defined as a measure of change in the measurement of variables which defines a building. Length, breadth, and height are amongst some of the measurement variables that could be used to define the shape of a building. The definition conforms to the explanation of index numbers by [15], [16]. A characteristic feature of index numbers which must be specified is the reference point, and is usually referred to as the “base” [19]. The reference point for time related phenomena is referred to as the base period. The base shape for most building shape index is a fundamental shape like the circle or square, although any shape can be used as a base provided the objective of the index is specified [5]. For example, the base shape for the volume compactness (VOLM) index is the hemisphere.

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From the foregoing, perimeter-area functions can be viewed in terms of index numbers. Perimeter-area functions or indexes shows the relationship between the perimeter and area of shapes and captures the measure of changes between the perimeter of a shape and the area of the shape. The perimeter-area function is important in quantities take-off and building measurement. The function is directly reflected in; or used to compute; the cost of several building elements such as floors, external walls, external foundation footings, and external finishes (painting, glazing, tiling, plastering). Likewise, the perimeter-area function is important in building allometry [20]. Horizontal distribution volumes and internal cube, which have significant relationships with mechanical and electrical services cost, as observed by [21], are also connected with the perimeter-area function of buildings. There are various indexes related to the shape, perimeter, and area of buildings in the literature. These indexes were developed with the main objective of measuring the cost effectiveness of building shapes [5].

B. Review of existing Building Shape Indexes

A summary of nine building shape indexes identified in the literature by [5], [22]–[24] is presented in Table I and are summarized next. The wall area to floor area (WFA) index provides the ratio between the area of the perimeter wall (i.e. the total length of external wall multiplied by the height of wall) and the area of the floor space within the perimeter wall. In relation to construction cost, it is expected that the lower the WFA index value, the lower cost of construction [23]. The wall to floor (WF) index provides the deviation between the perimeter of an orthogonal shape, and the perimeter of a square shape of the same area as the orthogonal shape. The WF index measures the efficiency of a plan shape using the square shape as a reference point [24]. The shape-effectiveness (SE) index provides the deviation between the perimeter of an orthogonal shape and the perimeter of a square shape of the same area as the orthogonal shape. Therefore, the SE index is similar to the WF index. The difference between SE and WF indexes is the formulae representation of the indexes. While the WF index uses only the perimeter to determine the index, the SE index uses the area of the shape directly in the index formulae. The lower the WF index value the more efficient the space-shape function.

The building planning “m” (m) index is a simplification of the perimeter and area of a shape into a non-unitary ratio. Since the perimeter of a building is measured in metres (m) and area is measured in square of metres (m²), the m index reduces the unit of the area to metres (i.e. m² x ½ = m). The reduction is a result of the differentiation of a quadratic function, thus yielding a linear function which has a common variable with the quadratic function. The m index is a simple non-unitary ratio. The m index for circular shapes is approximately 3.546 (3 sf) for any given radius, while the m index for rectangular shapes are always greater than 4. The square has an exact m index of 4. The length/breadth (LB)

index provides an efficiency ratio for any rectangular shaped plan. The lower the LB index value the more efficient the shape is with regards to the available area within the shape perimeter. The plan/shape (PS) index is an extension of the LB index. The PS index allows for multiple plan shapes by incorporating number of floors into the LB index. PS is well suited for multi-storey construction, and has been able to provide an average of LB index for multiple floors [24].

TABLE I
BUILDING SHAPE INDEXES AND FORMULAE

Index	Formulae
Wall area to floor area (WFA) ratio	$\frac{W}{F}$
Wall to floor (WF) index (J. Cook) *	$\frac{P - P_s}{P_s} \times 100\%$
Shape-effectiveness (SE) index (J. Cook) *	$\left(\frac{P}{4\sqrt{A}}\right) - 1$
Building planning ‘m’ index (m)	$\frac{P}{\sqrt{A}}$
Length/breadth (LB) Index (D. Banks of London South Bank University, formerly Polytechnic of South Bank) *	$P + \sqrt{P^2 - 16a}$ $P - \sqrt{P^2 - 16a}$
Plan/Shape (PS) Index (D. Banks) *	$g + \sqrt{P^2 - 16r}$ $g - \sqrt{P^2 - 16r}$
Plan compactness or POP ratio (POP) (Strathclyde University) *	$\frac{2\sqrt{\pi A}}{P} \times 100\%$
Volume/Mass/Block compactness (VOLM) index	$2\pi \left[\left[(3V / 2\pi)^{1/3} \right]^2 / A_u \right] \times 100\%$
Reciprocal plan shape (S_R) index [†]	$a_1 A + a_2 P$

*Names of persons or institutions associated with the development of the indexes in the literature; [†] S_R requires an empirical modelling technique such as ordinary least-square regression to obtain a_1 and a_2 ; W = Wall area, F = Floor area, P = Wall perimeter, P_s = Wall perimeter of a square with equal floor area with the given floor area, a = Floor area, r = Gross floor area divided by number of floors, A = Floor area, V = Volume of building, A_u = Floor area of the building excluding the ground floor area, a_1 = Marginal effect of area on cost, a_2 = Marginal effect of perimeter on cost.

The plan compactness ratio (POP) index uses the circle as a reference point for providing the efficiency ratio of the perimeter of any shape to the area of that shape. A lower POP index value indicates an inefficient plan shape. The VOLM index is a volume index for a building in relation to the volume of a hemisphere. The area of the ground floor is not included in the VOLM index [24]. The reciprocal plan shape (S_R) index is an empirical index modelled to capture the relationship between the perimeter and area as independent variables and not as a ratio, as in other indexes mentioned earlier. The marginal effects of area and perimeter; a_1 and a_2 , on cost must be derived empirically before the index can be applied. Reference [22] demonstrated that the index for 48 completed multi-storey buildings in Hong Kong can be given as $(0.129A - 0.620P) \times 10^{-5}$.

Fig. 1 Breadth (B) on coefficient of dimensions (k_c) graphs

III. RESEARCH METHOD

Previous researches [22], [23], [25] have used different methods to study building plan shapes. Reference [25] used regression analysis in the allometric analysis of archetypal buildings, and observed a strong relationship between the area and volumes of buildings. Similarly, [22] used regression analysis to establish the relationship between the cost, perimeter and area of buildings. Although both researchers used regression, the overall approach adopted in both studies was different. Reference [25] focused on the relationship between the surface area and volume of buildings by reproducing Ranko Bon's work theoretically; on the other hand, [22] focused on the effect of perimeter and area on cost. Both researches were empirical in nature and provided insightful results. Empirical observations are not neutral, and are determined by interpretations [26]. Interpretations of empirical observations might be subject to errors and bias, since observations and "facts" are independent of each other as posited by [26]. Thus, a means of verifying or validating the researcher's observation is important. Attempts should be made, whenever possible, to explain empirical observations by the use of both interpretation and scientific verification or validation [27]. Hence the current study adopts mathematical and empirical (Regression analysis) methods to validate and explain the observed relationship between the perimeter and area of building plan shapes.

A detailed literature review of existing building indexes was carried out to gain insight into the applications and derivation of existing indexes. The empirical relationship between the shortest length (breadth B) and area of a four-sided orthogonal polygon was established by comparing different measurement of breadth and different values of the coefficient of dimensions k_c for same area measurements. The approach in this study is similar in concept to Steadman's and Ranko Bon's allometric analysis of wall areas and floor areas to volume of buildings [25]. The approach used by Steadman was to construct theoretical buildings of various sizes that could be studied and analysed allometrically. On the other hand, Bon's allometric analysis was carried out by taking measurements of an existing 40 residential buildings [25]. The result obtained by the two researchers were similar, an indication that allometric analysis of theoretical buildings could be carried out with reliable results. In the current study, empirical analysis of theoretical orthogonal shapes was carried out. Upon discovery of the non-linear monotonic relationship between breadth and coefficient of dimensions, a mathematical approach was adopted to validate the observed relationship.

In order to develop the empirical model in this study, three variables are defined. The variables are: breadth, area and coefficient of dimensions. The breadth is defined as the shorter side of a four-sided orthogonal polygon with metre as the unit of measurement. The area is defined as the total two-dimensional surface enclosure within a four-sided orthogonal polygon and is measured as a square of metre. Lastly, the coefficient of dimensions (k_c) is defined as B/L , where B

is the shorter side and L is the longer side of a four-sided orthogonal polygon. k_c is a non-unitary variable. Various values of k_c were computed while varying the length and breadth of the rectangle, where $B \leq L$. It was observed that for any given area A , the breadth B is directly proportional to coefficient of dimensions k_c as a non-linear monotonic function (i.e. $B \propto k_c$). The results of the observations are shown in Fig. 1. The R-value of the regression lines for all areas ($1\text{m}^2, 3\text{m}^2, 10\text{m}^2, 15\text{m}^2, 20\text{m}^2, 100\text{m}^2, 1000\text{m}^2, 200\text{m}^2$) was 1; a very strong indication that k_c can explain all the variability around the mean value of B . Therefore, the general function for all observed trends is given as $y = \beta x^{0.5}$ where the value of β is 1, 3.1623, 3.873, 4.4721, 10, 14.142 and 31.623 for the area values of $1\text{ m}^2, 3\text{ m}^2, 10\text{ m}^2, 15\text{ m}^2, 20\text{ m}^2, 100\text{ m}^2, 200\text{ m}^2$, and 1000 m^2 , respectively. The coefficient β in each of the graphs corresponds to the square root of the area of the four-sided orthogonal polygon.

The graphs in Fig. 1 show the monotonic relationship between and for different areas A of a four-sided orthogonal polygon. Using $A=15\text{ m}^2$ as an example, when k_c is 0.10, 0.20, 0.80 and 1, B is 1.23 m, 1.73 m, 3.46 m and 3.87 m, respectively. The values of B increases as the value of k_c increases while A remains constant (i.e. $A=15\text{m}^2$) for all values of B and k_c . Similar observations were noted for all other areas (i.e. $1\text{ m}^2, 3\text{ m}^2, 20\text{ m}^2, 100\text{ m}^2, 200\text{ m}^2$, and 1000 m^2) all having different B values for the same k_c values. Varying the values of B will also affect the values of L (Length of shape), since the area of the shape must be constant for any value of B .

$$\text{Empirically, } B = \beta k_c^{0.5}, \text{ where } \beta \triangleq \sqrt{A} \quad (1)$$

A characteristic of a monotonic function such as $y = \beta x^{0.5}$ for $\{x \in \mathbb{R} : x > 0\}$ is that $\delta y / \delta x > 0$ for strictly increasing monotone functions.

$$\frac{\delta y}{\delta x} = \frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{x}}, \{x \in \mathbb{R} : x = 1\}, \frac{\delta y}{\delta x} = \frac{\beta}{2} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the empirical model (1) represents a non-linear monotonic relationship between breadth B , coefficient of dimensions k_c and area A of a four-sided orthogonal polygon. In order to validate the empirical model, and to establish a relationship between the length, breadth, perimeter, area and coefficient of dimensions, a mathematical approach is adopted in the next section.

IV. CONCEPTUAL PERIMETER MODEL

A. Development of Model

Defining a function $f(s) = qs + c$, in relation to a planar origin to describe a rectangle, where q is a zero slope and c is the intercept, the area and perimeter of the rectangular geometry is given as:

$$A = \int_R f(s) ds, R: a \leq x \leq b \quad (3)$$

$$P = 2 \left[\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^x \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds + \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^y \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds \right] \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the length and breadth of a four-sided orthogonal polygon can be written as (5) and (6), respectively.

$$L = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds \quad (5)$$

$$B = \int_{y_a}^{y_b} \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds \quad (6)$$

Defining coefficient of dimensions (k_c) as B/L , where $B \leq L$, and $0 < k_c \leq 1$. Using the area A of rectangle in (3), L and B can be defined in terms of A , and as shown in (7) and (10).

$$L = \frac{\int_{y_a}^{y_b} \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds}{k_c} \quad (7)$$

$$A = L \int_{y_a}^{y_b} \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds \quad (8)$$

$$A = \frac{\left(\int_{y_a}^{y_b} \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds \right)^2}{k_c} \quad (9)$$

$$B = \int_{y_a}^{y_b} \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) is similar to (1), and thus, validates the observed non-linear monotonic relationship between Breadth (B) and k_c . Based on (7) and (8), L can be rewritten as (11).

$$B = \int_{y_a}^{y_b} \sqrt{1 + [f'(s)]^2} ds \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the perimeter (4) of a four-sided orthogonal polygon can be rewritten as (12).

$$P = \frac{2 \int f(s) ds (k_c + 1)}{\left[k_c \int f(s) ds \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) is a conceptual perimeter model, and can be used to compute the girth of a building for any given area and k_c values, as later shown in the paper. Where k_c as a Subject of

formula can be expressed as $8A/\sqrt{P^4 - 16A.P^2} - 8A + P^2$.

Equation (12) can be incorporated into quantities based pre-design cost models for estimating quantities of external walls, glazing, edge foundations, and external finishes.

B. Validation of Model

Building plans are designed to various shapes and sizes; a heterogeneous characteristic of building projects. Therefore, the developed conceptual perimeter model must be applicable to various shapes and sizes to be a useful model. Models are designed for specific purposes [28], [29], and must be able to imitate or reproduce real and observed situation or phenomena based on a given input [27], [30]. The eight shapes shown in Fig. 2 were constructed to validate the conceptual perimeter model. The constructed shapes are of different configurations in order to simulate the heterogeneous nature of building plans. All the orthogonal shapes have an equal area of 9 m² with different perimeters. A script (see Fig. 3) was written using the Python programming language to implement and execute the conceptual perimeter model on all the constructed orthogonal shapes. The k_c values of the different shapes were computed and used as inputs for the conceptual perimeter function.

Fig. 2 Orthogonal shapes

The computer output of the conceptual perimeter function for all the eight orthogonal shapes is presented in Table II. The precision of the conceptual perimeter model was evaluated using the absolute percentage error ($|A_p - C_p| / A_p \cdot 100\%$), where A_p and C_p are the actual and conceptual perimeters of the constructed orthogonal shapes, respectively. The error values show the deviation of the conceptual perimeter from the actual perimeter. The error value for shape b was 0%. However, it must be noted that the error values (0.001% to 0.004%) for other shapes was due to rounding-off errors of the computed values used in computing the conceptual perimeter. There is no current study to the knowledge of the researchers that can be used as a benchmark for model evaluation; nonetheless, the developed model shows a reliable performance on the constructed orthogonal shapes.

```

1 '''
2 FUNCTION FOR TESTING CONCEPTUAL PERIMETER MODEL
3 '''
4 #Description :This will compute the coefficient of dimensions and perimeter
5 # of any orthogonal polygon
6 #Author :iOSEun
7 #Python_version :3.6
8 =====
9
10 #Import math module
11 import math
12
13 #Function for coefficient of dimensions (kc)
14 def KC (shape, A, P): # A means area, P means perimeter
15     kcx = 8*A / (math.sqrt(abs(P**4 - 16*A*P**2)) - 8*A + P**2)
16     kcx = '{0:.4g}'.format(kcx)
17     kcx = float(kcx)
18     print ('if the area and perimeter of shape ' + shape + ' is ' + str(A) +
19           'm2 and ' + str(P) + 'm, then,')
20     print ('Calculated kc index of shape ' + shape + ' is:', kcx)
21     return kcx
22
23 #Calculation of kc values for various othogonal shapes
24 kc_a = KC('a', 9, 18)
25 kc_b = KC('b', 9, 12)
26 kc_c = KC('c', 9, 20)
27 kc_d = KC('d', 9, 14)
28 kc_e = KC('e', 9, 20)
29 kc_f = KC('f', 9, 20)
30 kc_g = KC('g', 9, 16)
31 kc_h = KC('h', 9, 20)
32
33 #Function for conceptual perimeter
34 def Concept_Perimeter(kc, A):# A means area
35     P = 2*A*(kc+1)/(math.sqrt(A*kc))
36     P = '{0:.6g}'.format(P)
37     print (P)
38     return P
39
40 #Testing of conceptual perimeter function on various orthogonal shapes
41 Concept_Perimeter(kc_a, 9)
42 Concept_Perimeter(kc_b, 9)
43 Concept_Perimeter(kc_c, 9)
44 Concept_Perimeter(kc_d, 9)
45 Concept_Perimeter(kc_e, 9)
46 Concept_Perimeter(kc_f, 9)
47 Concept_Perimeter(kc_g, 9)
48 Concept_Perimeter(kc_h, 9)
49
50 #End of script
51 =====

```

Fig. 3 Python script for testing conceptual perimeter model

TABLE II
PERIMETER, AREA AND k_c OF DIFFERENT ORTHOGONAL SHAPES IN FIG. 2

Orthogonal shape	Area (m ²)	Perimeter (m)	k_c	Conceptual Perimeter (m)	Absolute percentage error (%)
a	9	18	0.1459	17.9999	0.001
b	9	12	1.0000	12.000	0.000
c	9	20	0.1111	20.0008	0.004
d	9	14	0.3201	13.9996	0.003
e	9	20	0.1111	20.0008	0.004
f	9	20	0.1111	20.0008	0.004
g	9	16	0.2038	15.9994	0.004
h	9	20	0.1111	20.0008	0.004

V. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The present study was designed to develop a model that could be used to estimate the perimeter of building plans at the conceptual stage of building projects. In the process, the relationship between the breadth and k_c was explored. Based on empirical evidence in this study, it was found that the relationship between the shortest length and coefficient of dimensions (k_c) of a four-sided orthogonal polygon is a strictly monotonic function. This implies that for any four-sided orthogonal polygon with given area, the breadth (shortest side) decreases monotonically as the length increases in a non-linear manner. The square shape has a k_c value of 1 and a perimeter-

area efficiency of 100%. Theoretically, the “circle” has the shortest perimeter for a given area, but due to buildability and constructability challenges with circular shapes, construction of curved or circular walls and elements are not efficient [5], [22].

The observed non-linear monotonic relationship between the shortest side-length and k_c of a four-sided orthogonal polygon was validated in the study by (10). One interesting finding is that the value of k_c was the reciprocal of the LB index value. While the value of k_c ranged between 0 and 1, the values of LB index ranged from 1 to ∞ (infinity). The conceptual perimeter model (12) can be used at pre-design stage to provide the measurement estimate of building elements and preliminaries items that are directly related with building envelopes; for example, scaffolding works and perimeter safety netting.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The perimeter-area function of buildings is very important in the estimation of building element quantities. The function is useful in cost models and in building economics. The aim of the current research was to obtain the girth of building envelopes at early pre-design stage. The use of perimeter or girth of buildings at the conceptual stage for estimating conceptual quantities has not been exhaustively researched. Conceptual quantities have been shown to improve the accuracy of conceptual cost models, and it is a research area to be explored in cost modelling. This paper focused on using gross floor area to determine the perimeter of any orthogonal shaped building before sketch designs are produced. A monotonic relationship was found between the shortest length and coefficient of dimensions for a four sided orthogonal polygon. Using an empirical approach, and mathematical validation, an equation for conceptual perimeter was established. Equation (12), termed “conceptual perimeter equation”, is a mathematical model that can be used at the pre-design stage to estimate conceptual material quantities of items related to building envelopes. Quantities such as the external wall area, external finishing area and scaffolding area can be estimated before sketch designs are produced. Currently, the conceptual perimeter equation is suitable for single floor plans or where the floor plans of multiple floors have identical area and shape. The implementation of the conceptual perimeter equation for multiple floor plans of different areas and shapes could be explored in future studies.

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